

**DESCRIPTION OF WOMAN CONCEPT IN HOUSEHOLD AND SOCIETY
CONCEPT IN ABDULLA KAHHAR'S PROSE**

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Abstract. The female character created in the works of Abdulla Kahhar was mainly formed under the influence of the literary traditions, dominant ideology and ideology of her time. This feature was determined by the researchers who studied the author's work through different analysis of his female image.

Key words: Abdulla Kahhar, novel, woman concept, female image, female character, the concept of household, freedom.

It is significant that in the works of Abdulla Kahhar, the issue of the female character is described in harmony with the tenets of critical realism and brutal realism in literary works. In this, the concept of woman is more noticeable as it is depicted as the basis of the concepts of household, family, society and individual. Through this, it becomes clear that the character of women is illuminated in proportion to the laws of the social society.

In the work of the writer, the characters of two types, i.e. intelligent and light-natured women, are highlighted.

In the works of Abdulla Kahhar, the evolution and development of the female character can be observed throughout the works. As a result, different character types of women appeared in literary works. Each type of character dissonance is shown to be perfected in the process of moving from one work to another. For example, most female character types in the writer's historical stories are passive, while some of them are embodied in a combative, active form under the influence of social changes in society. Unsin in the story "Horror" ("Daxshat") is such a fighting, fearless, brave female character.

The criteria of the female character developed in the works of Abdulla Kahhar are also significant in that they can be used to classify them into types and to compare

them with the female characters in the works of other Uzbek writers. In particular, the character and image creation criteria used by the writer are important in revealing the specific qualities of the female character and determining whether they belong to a certain type. Such criteria serve as a basis for analyzing the features of the female character depicted in the works and determining their characteristic of a certain type. In this regard, female character types, including girls, brides, brides, wives, mistresses, mothers, sisters, mothers-in-law, aunts, grandmothers, old women, female leaders, employees, maids, and daily companions, presented in literary works, attract special attention. According to the fact that each of them was formed in different environments and conditions, in different families, at different stages of society, they show their important qualities in terms of their activities and outlook. For example, Unsin comes from a poor family to a rich family as a second wife. But she cannot be a wife or mistress. It's just a rich man's pastime. That is why her character does not show signs related to the status of a wife, that is, a real life partner in the family, and the character status of the mistress of the family. Because he could achieve this only if he showed the corresponding tasks.

If you pay attention, Unsin, despite being young, will have an argument with her old husband. This negative trait did not suddenly appear in his character. This state of mind in him is created by the family environment of the dodkhoh, to whom Unsin became a bride, and his negative attitude towards his wives. Although this rebellion that arose in him was passive, it was natural that it gradually spread to others. This situation is shown in the example of Nadirmohbegim's demonstratively leaving the dodkhoh's house together with Unsin's dead body.

So, it is possible to witness that the character and fate of women who have faced various destinies are artistically reflected in the works of Abdulla Kahhar. But in the works of the writer, women who are interpreted as social types (leading women like Saida, women who fight for the fate of other women like Maston) as well as women of the second level (women who hesitate to change their fate like Turgunoy, servant

women) are depicted. Of course, this shows that they differ according to their function.

The ideal characters of the active type depicted by Abdulla Kahhar are often clearly visible in his works on modern themes. In revealing the nature of modern female characters, the author approached their modern clothing, attitude to the news of the time, and their speech from the typological side, and described each of them in a unique, unique way. This, at the same time, made it possible to clearly understand the purpose of the writer. For example, in the story "Jonfig'on" it is described that Malohat graduated from the driving course, drove a truck, was awarded three times in two years for this progress, and his photo was hung as a large portrait among the proud stakhanovs of the city.

The character of a learned woman described in the works of Abdulla Kahhar can be seen in the example of Munishkhan in the novel "Sarob" and Saida in the short story "Saida".

Maston's character in the story "Maston" shows the events of selfless but simple characters who care for the fate of others. For example, his story about a person who eats a lizard being a "pes" shows that he is naive and gullible.

In the works of Abdulla Kahhar, the characters of mothers were brought to light through various motives formed by the different performance of motherhood. For example, the story "Pomegranate" shows the unique whimsical character of the expectant mother, while the story "Nurli Choghilar" shows the image of Zuhra, who raised a poor girl as a result of neglecting her daughter's education, and as a result, this poor girl could not be a good mother for her child.

The writer's stories "Old women knocked on the wire", "Asror grandfather", "Thief" ("Kampirlar sim qoqdi", "Asror bobo", "Bemor") are notable for the character types of Uzbek mothers and old mothers.

Generally speaking, in the work of the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Kahhar, both creative and negative vices of women are revealed in different ways on the

example of different female characters. In this, women's social role and character traits are given special attention and revealed in chronological order.

The role of women in human relationships, unity with men, and gender equality, observed in the creative prose of the artist, have a special interpretation.

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